

The Implementation of Curriculum 2013 in English Subject at SMA Negeri in Ternate

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Abstract

This research focused on the implementation of curriculum 2013 in English subject at SMA Negeri in Ternate. In Ternate, curriculum 2013 has implemented in some senior high school that the researcher took as samples in this research. This research used qualitative approach with descriptive method. The population of this research are 12 SMA in Ternate. And the samples of this research are 3 (three) of 12 SMA in Ternate. The data collection used in this research are: observation, questionnaire, and documentation. To analyze the data, the researcher used reduction data, presentation data, and verification data. The implementation of K 13 in English subject in school A and C Ternate can be neglected because the K 13 is not implemented. The implementation of K 13 in English subject in school B Ternate is implemented. The learning process of English based on lesson plan. From 9 items of main activities based on lesson plan there were 8 activities implemented and only one activity didn't implemented it was basic competence and indicator. Hereby the researchers take conclusion that the implementation of K13 in English subject in school B is good

Keywords: *curriculum 2013, English subject.*

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1. Background

Implementation is a process of applying ideas, concepts, policies, or innovations in the form of practical actions to give effect, in the form of changes in knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. In the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, it is stated that the implementation is „put something into effect“. Implementation of the curriculum can also be interpreted as the actualization of the written curriculum in the form of learning. Line with what Miller and Sellar said that in some cases, implementation has been identified with the instruction.

The definition of implementation above is not just talking about activity or action but how about the activity have planned and carried out to achieve the objective of the activity. The implementation has an object that influences it, so it does not alone. The object meant is curriculum. It is true if curriculum is an object of implementation. It is stated in UU number 20 of 2003 year about the national education system that the curriculum definition is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the purposes, contents, teaching materials, and methods used to guide the implementation of learning activities to achieve specific goals of education.

In the implementation of curriculum 2013, teacher and headmaster are two important elements in the successful of the implementation of curriculum 2013. Headmaster, as the principle, has successfully implemented the curriculum 2013 especially in her/his duty and authority at the school. By curriculum, teaching and learning process will structurally and systematically to reach the learning objective.

Through the curriculum 2013 in Indonesia, in this research the researchers focused on the implementation of curriculum 2013 in English subject at SMA Kota Ternate. In Ternate, curriculum 2013 has implemented in some senior high school that the researcher took as samples in this research. The result of observation and pre interview about the implementation of K13 in Ternate are: there were some headmasters and teachers still confused about the implementation of K13, the English teachers didn't make the learning device completely, teaching and learning process occurred through talkative and the teachers more dominant than students, many teachers are not showed the creativity in learning, and the evaluation done by the teachers still emphasized just in cognitive aspect not authentic. Based on the explanation, the researchers want to make a research for describe how the implementation of K13 is in English subject at SMA in Ternate

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Curriculum 2013

Curriculum 2013 exist as a result of completing previous curriculums which have been standard of education process in Indonesia. Not less than 10 curriculum ever exist in curriculum development in this country with each different characteristics. Despite those different characteristics exist, the existance of curriculums which have been produced by education expert in this country aiming at improving education quality of Indonesia.

Based on Indonesia regulation no 20 in 2003 about national education system of Indonesia curriculum is a set of plan and rules regarding to objective, content, and learning process and also method to be used as guideline of learning activity application to reach certain objectives. Curriculum 2013 developed based on internal and external factors. The internal factors existed because of education demand refer to 8 national education standard which covers content standard, standard process, graduate competence standard, personel standard and education, infrastructure standard, management standard, standard for education funding, and educational asesment standard. The external factors are related to globalisation issues and others about environmental, technology and information development, the rise of culture and creative industry (Permendikbud no 69 Tahun 2013).

Changes and development around the world forced Indonesia as one of developing country try to adapt to be in line with other developed country. To fulfill the 8 national standard of education proclaimed, Indonesia which in process of changs proved that we continously improved our education system so that's why curriculum 2013 exist to fulfill the 8 national standar of education. Globalisation

flow also become the major part which should be responded fast by Indonesia by place education stead so that Indonesia could face the globalisation flow.

Compared to the curriculum KTSP in 2006, curriculum 2013 has different characteristics which doesn't available in curriculum KTSP in 2006. Here are the characteristics of curriculum 2013 cited from Permendikbud no 69 Tahun 2013.

1. Developing a balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills, and applying them in various situations in the school and community.
2. Putting the school as part of the community that provide a learning experience so the learners are able to apply what is learned in the school to the community and utilize the community as a learning resource.
3. Developing attitude, knowledge and skill and to apply those in various situation in schools and societies.
4. Giving freely enough time to develop a variety of attitudes, knowledge, and skills.
5. Developing the competencies expressed in terms of class core competencies which is specified more in basic competence of subjects.
6. Developing class core competence into organizing elements of basic competence. All the basic competencies and learning processes are developed to achieve the competence stated in core competencies.
7. Developing a basic competence based on the accumulative principle, mutually reinforced and enriched between-subjects and education level (horizontal and vertical organizations).

As it describes above, curriculum 2013 definetely has different characteristic compared to curriculum 20016 for example there is balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills. balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills, balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills,T balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills, balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills, balance between spiritual and social attitudes, knowledge, and skills. Teachers should be able to transfer and build these four competencies of student creatively so that the students not only get the knowledge but enrich themselves with faith, good morale, and skills from school. In addition curriculum 2013 place school as the part of society so students could learn from society and use their knowledge for the sake of society. Beside the characteristics above, the curriculum 2013 also has its' objectives amanded in Permendikbud no 69 Tahun 2013.

The objective of curriculum 2013 is generating Indonesian people which are: productive, creative, innovative, affective; through the strengthening of attitudes, skills, and knowledge which are integrated. Based on the theme, the implementation of 2013 curriculum is expected to produce a productive, creative, and innovative human. The curriculum of 2013 also has it's structures of curriculum there are;

1. Core competency

The core competency is designed based on students' age on each level. Through core competency, vertical integration from different class are able to be secured. Core competency formula used are Core competency 1 (KI-1) for spiritual competency, core competency 2 (KI-2) for social competency, core competency 3 (KI-3) for knowledge competency, and core competency 4 (KI-4) for skill competency.

2. Basic competency

Basic competency is designed to meet the core competency. The formula of basic competency is developed by considering the students' characteristic, initial ability and subject characteristic. Basic competency is divided into 4 groups based on core competency grouping as follows; group 1 describing core competency 1, group 2 describe core competency 2, group 3 describe core competency 3 and group 4 describe core competency 4.

2.2. The implementation of curriculum 2013 in english subject of senior high school

Curriculum implementation is a process of how curriculum works (Beauchamp, 1975:164) and also an implementation form of idea, program, or new activity planning to people or organisation (Miller & Seller, 1985: 246). Starting on 2013/2014 this curriculum was implemented on schools in Indonesia gradually. The implementation itself lean on amandement of Permendikbud no 81A year 2013 stated;

Article 1

The implementation of 2013 curriculum on primary schools/madrasah ibtidaiyah (SD/MI), junior high school / madrasah tsanawiyah (SMP/MTs), senior high school /madrasah aliyah (SMA/MA), and vocational high school/ vocational madrasah aliyah (SMK/MAK) should be conducted in several stages and started in 2013 / 2014.

Article 1

Curriculum implementation in SD/MI, SMP/MTs, SMA/MA, and SMK/MAK. Use the implementation of curriculum guidelines that covers:

1. Guidelines for preparing and management of school curriculum KTSP.
2. Guideline of the development of local charge.
3. Guideline of extracurricular activities.
4. General guidelines of learning and.
5. Guideline for curriculum evaluation.

The reason of curriculum development regarding 1. Future challenge, 2. Future competence, 3. Public perception, 4. The development of knowledge as well as pedagogy, and 5. Negative phenomena presented. The implementation of this curriculum is in line with government rules Permendikbud no 81A tahun 2013 that requires the application of curriculum 2013 began in 2013/2014. Some appointed schools tried out the curriculum. For about 6221 tried-out school applying this curriculum pointed by Kemendiknas and later to be evaluated whether this curriculum

are able to be implemented nationally or not. At the beginning of its application, curriculum 2013 attracting more polemics from practitioners of education starting from teachers and educational experts. With strong belief, somehow, the implementation of curriculum 2013 firstly reached only 3% then increase to 6% as well as the decrease of the use of curriculum 2006 to 75%. This is the reason why then the optimism of other schools in region continue to implement the curriculum 2013 including schools in Ternate. As has already been mentioned before that the content of curriculum 2013 is based on Permendikbud no 69 year 2013. Indonesia ministry of education and culture decision no 096 year 1967 stated that English is the first foreign language, therefore this subject is included as subject in Indonesia curriculum.

On the new curriculum, the teaching of English inclined the act of knowledge and skill where this act developed in teaching and learning process. Students' are given the opportunity to express their knowledges and skills not only riveted on theory.

In reality, however the purpose of English teaching and learning should be in line with content standard based on government rule no 19. English subject also should be based on core competence, elaborated more in basic competence and realized in a syllabus and to be interpreted in the form of lesson plan. A lesson plan then become the guidance for teachers when applying english subject in the classroom. The content of english subject in curriculum 2013 are available at Permendikbud no 69 Tahun 2013 page 80.

From this basic competence formulation so the formulation of the syllabus as well as the lesson plan sourced. The teaching and learning process is easier to be applied because the basic competence is formulated in detail. Even if teacher wants to explore material and activities learning whatsoever can be implemented as long in accordance with competence of formulated before.

12 high schools in Ternate has largely apply the curriculum 2013. There are benefits of the curriculum 2013 application so far so this become the reason why the researchers are intended to observe how the implementation of curriculum 2013 in school. In deed tteachers as the engine of the sustainability and the successful of curriculum 2013 is expected to bring their culture in accordance with components of core competence and basic competence and the drawn up syllabus. Whether the graduate standard which has been determined really met the fact in field? Based on those questions, researchers want to know how is the application of curriculum 2013 in english subject of senior high school in Ternate.

3. Method

This research used qualitative approach with descriptive method. According to Moleong in Bogdan and Taylor (1975), say that qualitative research as research procedure that produced descriptive data likes written words or oral from the people and behavior that can observed. So, can conclude that this research is descriptive qualitative research. This research showed to describe the

implementation of curriculum 2013 in English subject at some SMA in Ternate. Through qualitative approach, the data be obtain completely, deeper, and meaningful so it can be reach the objective of the research.

The population of this research are 12 SMA in Ternate. And the samples of this research are 3 (three) of 12 SMA in Ternate.

The data collection used in this research are: observation, quetionaire, and documentation. To analyze the data, the researcher used model of tehniqe analysis data according to Miles & Huberman. There are some steps to analyze the data. They are: reduction data, presentation data, and verification data.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Observations Result

The researchers analyze the 9 items based on lesson plan; there are core competencies, basic competences and indicators, learning objective, learning, teaching method, learning media, learning sources, learning activities and evaluation. Based on the observation result at A, B, and C school found that, in school A all of the item are not suitable. School B has one not suitable item it is on basic competences and indicators. School C have only one suitable item based on lesson plan, it is core competencies. The detailed information displayed on the table below;

Table 1.1
 Observation result

No	SMA	SUITABLE	NOT SUITABLE
1	A	0	9
2	B	8	1
3	C	1	8

4.2. Documentation result

On the documentation result, the researchers only focus on Syllabus and Lesson plan document, whether the teachers have the document or not. The result showed that, all of the three schools have the syllabus and lesson plan document. The detailed information is displayed in the table below:

Table 1.2
 Documentation result

NO	SMA	AVAILABLE	NOT AVAILABLE
1	A	1	0
2	B	1	0
3	C	1	0

4.3. Questionnaire result

This questionnaire consisted of two types of questionnaires. They are for the English teachers and students. The questionnaire for teachers aimed at finding six main indicators of teachers' respond toward the implementation of curriculum 2013. The indicators are curriculum understanding, learning devices, learning implementation, scientific approach, sources, and evaluation. The result of questionnaire from the teachers in three schools showed in the table below;

Table1.3
 Teachers' questionnaire result

NO	SCHOOL	INDICATORS	Positive Respos	PERCENTAGE	DECISION
1	A	the curriculum comprehension	3 of 3 statements	100%	Very good
2		learning devices	6 of 7 statements	86%	Very good
3		learning implementation	6 of 6 statements	100%	Very good
4		scientific approach	7 of 7 statements	100%	Very good
5		sources	4 of 4 statements	100%	Very good
6		evaluation	3 of 4 statements	75%	Good
7	B	the curriculum comprehension	3 of 3 statements	100%	Very good
8		learning devices	7 of 7 statements	100%	Very good
9		learning implementation	5 of 6 statements	83%	Very good
10		scientific approach	7 of 7 statements	100%	Very good
11		sources	2 of 4 statements	50%	Not good
12		evaluation	3 of 4 statements	75%	Good
13	C	the curriculum comprehension	3 of 3 statements	100%	Very good
14		learning devices	7 of 7 statements	100%	Very good
15		learning implementation	5 of 6 statements	83%	Very good
16		scientific approach	7 of 7 statements	100%	Very good
17		sources	4 of 4 statements	100%	Very good
		evaluation	4 of 4 statements	100%	Very good

Based on table above the conclusion is the average of teachers' respond from three schools toward the questionnaire is very good.

Students questionnaire result of School A is 50 % students agree that the implementation of teaching and learning process by the teacher is suitable, school B is 47.8% students are very agree that the implementation of teaching and learning process by the teacher is suitable, and school C 55,6% students are very agree that the implementation of teaching and learning process by the teacher is suitable. Based on the students' questionnaire result of three schools showed that students are very agree that the implementation of teaching and learning English by the teacher are suitable with curriculum 2013.

4.4. Discussions

The researchers realize that there are similar responses between teachers' and students' questionnaire result but the students' respond is caused by how the teacher implement the teaching and learning process somehow the students didn't understand how the implementation of K 13 should be so the student questionnaire result can be neglected. In addition, teachers' response toward the implementation of K 13 is very good but it is contradictive with the researchers' observation result. Hereby the researchers conclude that;

1. The implementation of K 13 in English subject in school A and C Ternate can be neglected because the K 13 is not implemented
2. The implementation of K 13 in English subject in school B Ternate is implemented. The learning process of English based on lesson plan. From 9 items of main activities based on lesson plan there were 8 activities implemented and only one activity didn't implemented it was basic competence and indicator. Hereby the researchers take conclusion that the implementation of K13 in English subject in school B is good.

5. Conclusion

Observation result and documentation result in three schools at Ternate showed that the implementation of Curriculum 2013 in English subject at school A, School B and School C are different. All school (school A, B and C) have document of syllabus and lesson plan. The result of school A showed that 9 steps of learning activity in lesson plan based on K13 there were not done by the teacher. In school B, just 8 of 9 steps of learning activity was done by the teacher, while in school C just 1 of 9 step of learning activity was done by the teacher.

Based on the data of the result have explained, the researcher found that there are the differentiation between the implementation and understanding of the implementation of K13 in English subject. The learning step was done by the teachers come from the teachers character althought still based on lesson plan, and the next research relate to the teachers' character to

formulate the indicators in lesson plan will interest to do. The researchers hope, this results can be reference to the similar research in future.

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